

Graphical Abstract

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Highlights

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- Proposes a lightweight outlier removal algorithm for pose graph optimization
- Leverages path redundancy to validate pose consistency without global optimization
- Introduces a Weighted IQR model for reliability-aware outlier detection
- Separates rotation and translation filtering for improved detection precision

A Weighted IQR-based Outlier Detection Algorithm for Pose Graphs

Zhitao Wu^{a,1}, Guangyu Liu^{a,*}

^aDepartment of Automation, Hangzhou Dianzi University, Hangzhou, 310018, Zhejiang, China

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ABSTRACT

Robustness against outlier measurements is essential for improving the accuracy and consistency of pose graph optimization (PGO) and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM). This paper presents a lightweight outlier removal algorithm for pose transformations, which combines path redundancy with a Weighted Interquartile Range (Weighted IQR) strategy to effectively eliminate abnormal edges in pose graphs. Multiple redundant relative pose transformations between a pair of nodes are constructed through alternative paths using a path planning algorithm, providing statistically diverse yet related measurements. Each transformation is decomposed into rotation and translation components, which are processed independently using a reliability-weighted IQR method to identify and reject outliers. The algorithm adaptively incorporates noise tolerance thresholds to prevent over-rejection of data affected by regular sensor noise. Compared with traditional robust optimization and deep-learning-based detection approaches, the proposed method requires no prior training data or heavy optimization procedures, offering high interpretability and computational efficiency. Numerical experiments on randomly generated graphs demonstrate that the proposed algorithm achieves near-perfect recall when the outlier ratio is below 15%. Furthermore, when integrated with conventional graph optimization frameworks such as GTSAM, the algorithm enhances the trajectory accuracy and stability of SLAM back-end estimation, confirming its practical applicability to real-world robotic systems.

1. Introduction

In pose graph optimization (PGO) and SLAM back-end optimization, the effective detection and removal of outlier edges is a critical issue for ensuring the robustness and accuracy of the system. The presence of outlier edges may lead to divergence in the optimization process, distortion of the map structure, and significant degradation in localization accuracy. Accordingly, recent research on this problem has primarily focused on robust optimization models, graph-theoretic heuristic methods, deep learning approaches, and probabilistic consistency analysis.

Early approaches typically employed robust cost functions (e.g., Huber, Tukey, Cauchy) to mitigate the influence of outlier observations on the overall optimization. Carlone et al. Carlone and Calafiore (2018) proposed a robust graph optimization method based on convex relaxation, which is capable of producing near-optimal solutions without relying on initialization. Subsequently, Yang and Carlone Yang and Carlone (2023) developed STRIDE, a certifiably globally optimal optimization framework that integrates semidefinite programming (SDP) with a Total Least Squares (TLS) cost function, demonstrating stable performance even under 60% – 90% outlier ratios. Moreover, TEASER++ Yang, Shi and Carlone (2021) introduced a cascaded estimation strategy that decouples scale, rotation, and translation, and incorporates maximum clique detection for outlier rejection, establishing itself as a highly robust method for point cloud registration. Numerous studies have formulated outlier edge detection as a graph-theoretic problem. Mangelson et al. Mangelson, Dominic, Eustice and Vasudevan (2018) proposed the Pairwise Consistent Measurement (PCM) method,

which identifies mutually consistent constraint sets by constructing a consistency graph and solving for the maximum clique. Distributed consistency verification mechanisms have been employed in approaches such as DOOR-SLAM Lajoie, Ramtoula, Chang, Carlone and Beltrame (2020) and Kimera-Multi Chang, Tian, How and Carlone (2021), Tian, Chang, Arias, Nieto-Granda, How and Carlone (2022), effectively eliminating inter-robot false loop closures in multi-robot systems. Wu et al. Wu and Beltrame (2020) introduced the Cluster-based Penalty Scaling method, which evaluates local consistency through edge clustering and adjusts edge weights accordingly to enhance overall robustness.

Lee et al. Lee, Fraundorfer and Pollefeys (2013) reformulated robust graph optimization as a Classification Expectation-Maximization (Classification EM) problem by introducing hidden variables to estimate the reliability of edges, thereby adaptively adjusting edge weights during the EM update process. Similarly, Cai et al. Cai, Wei, Li and Wang (2025) proposed a consistency-based confidence factor model, which significantly enhances robustness through the integration of weighting factors and a classification mechanism. Furthermore, Feng et al. Feng, Liu, Cui and Fang (2024) introduced a two-stage initialization combined with a covariance scaling graph optimization framework, which incorporates M-estimation and an adaptive adjustment mechanism to effectively suppress the influence of outlier constraints. Agarwal et al. Agarwal, Tipaldi, Spinello, Stachniss and Burgard (2013) introduced the Dynamic Covariance Scaling (DCS) mechanism, which adaptively adjusts edge covariances during the optimization process to mitigate error propagation. Huang et al. Huang, Yang, Zhao, Lai and Hu (2019) proposed a constraint pruning method

 g.liu@hdu.edu.cn (G. Liu)
ORCID(s):

that integrates cluster consistency with maximal clique detection. Kang et al. Kang, Kim, Chung, Choi and Kim (2024) presented an efficient GNC scheduling strategy that identifies convex boundary points to avoid redundant iterations, thereby significantly improving graph optimization efficiency.

In recent years, end-to-end graph optimization based on Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) has emerged as a prominent research direction. Li et al. Li and Ling (2021) proposed the PoGO-Net, which encodes graph structures as neural network inputs and achieves robust pose estimation through iterative rotation averaging and an edge dropout mechanism. Gong et al. Gong, Xiao, Shi, Chen and Yu (2024) introduced MSGA-Net, which employs a multi-layer sparse graph attention mechanism to perform hierarchical interactive modeling of dynamic graphs, demonstrating superior performance in feature matching and camera pose estimation. Damblon et al. Damblon, Pollefeys and Barath (2025) utilized a Transformer-based architecture to classify graph edges, addressing memory constraints in large-scale graph processing by converting the graph into a line graph and applying a clustering mechanism. Integrated systems such as LAMP 2.0 Chang, Ebadi, Denniston, Ginting, Rosinol, Reinke, Palieri, Shi, Chatterjee, Morrell, akbar Aghamohammadi and Carlone (2022) and RELEAD Chen, Chen, Qi, Zhong, Feng and Wu (2024) have demonstrated the significance of robust back-end optimization in multi-robot and subterranean environments. IPC Olivastri and Pretto (2024) employs an incremental consistency evaluation mechanism, incorporating veto authority to enhance the robustness of edge selection. Furthermore, classical SLAM back-end approaches, including Switchable Constraints Sünderhauf and Protzel (2012), Max-Mixture, and RRR, have been widely applied in robust optimization and have shown competitive performance in various comparative studies Latif, Cadena and Neira (2014).

Building upon existing work, this paper proposes a lightweight anomaly detection algorithm based on path redundancy and the Weighted Interquartile Range (Weighted IQR), aimed at eliminating abnormal pose transformation edges in SLAM or sensor networks. The proposed method does not require training data, nor does it depend on deep neural networks or complex optimization models, thereby offering good interpretability and practical deployability. By constructing multiple redundant measurements within the graph, relative transformations between the same pair of nodes are obtained through diverse paths, introducing redundant information. Subsequently, the Weighted IQR statistical method is employed to remove outlier measurements that deviate significantly from the main distribution. This mechanism effectively mitigates the error amplification caused by the propagation of Gaussian noise and enables reliable detection of anomalous edges without significantly increasing computational complexity.

The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- **A lightweight statistical outlier removal framework.** Unlike conventional robust optimization or deep learning-based methods, the proposed algorithm is entirely parameter-free and does not rely on training data or complex non-convex solvers. It provides an interpretable and computationally efficient mechanism for eliminating abnormal relative pose transformations.
- **Integration of path redundancy for pose consistency validation.** The method constructs multiple redundant transformation paths between node pairs within the graph, effectively leveraging topological redundancy to evaluate the internal consistency of pose measurements. This redundancy-based evaluation enhances robustness without requiring global optimization.
- **Weighted Interquartile Range (Weighted IQR) for probabilistic reliability modeling.** A novel weighted variant of the IQR is introduced, in which each candidate transformation is assigned a reliability weight derived from sensor variance or path composition probability. This allows adaptive adjustment of statistical thresholds and improves the discrimination between true measurements and outliers.
- **Decoupled translation and rotation analysis for improved detection accuracy.** The proposed framework separates translation and rotation components in SE(3) estimation and applies dedicated weighted statistical filtering to each component, thereby achieving higher outlier rejection precision under non-Gaussian noise conditions.
- **Scalable and incrementally deployable architecture.** The algorithm can be executed iteratively or locally within SLAM back-end optimization. It supports incremental updates as new edges are introduced, making it suitable for large-scale or multi-robot scenarios where real-time robustness is critical.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 defines the problem and presents a specific illustrative example. Section 3 presents the proposed method in detail, including the algorithmic design and implementation details. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and discusses possible directions for future work.

2. Problem Formulation

In SLAM algorithms, each keyframe is typically treated as a node, and sensor data are utilized to estimate the relative pose transformations $T \in \text{SE}(3)$ between different keyframes. These pose transformations correspond to the edges connecting the nodes, thereby enabling the representation of the system as a graph. However, some of these transformations may be outliers, resulting in edges that are inconsistent with the rest of the graph.

A similar issue arises in sensor networks. In the problem of sensor network localization, each sensor is represented as a node, and sensors are capable of measuring the relative pose transformations between themselves and other nodes. Accordingly, the sensor network can also be modeled as a graph, where nodes represent sensors and edges correspond to the measured pose transformations. Due to factors such as measurement noise, some of these relative transformations may be outliers, leading to edges that are incompatible with the rest of the graph. To address this, an algorithm is proposed to eliminate the pose transformations that are considered outliers, or to remove the corresponding inconsistent edges from the graph.

An illustrative example of the problem is shown in Fig. 1, which depicts a scenario involving four nodes. A dashed line between any two nodes represents a relative pose measurement. The pose transformation is represented by a rotation-translation matrix $T \in SE(3)$. There are three measurements between node 1 and node 2, yielding the poses $T_{12}^1, T_{12}^2, T_{12}^3 \in SE(3)$. Similarly, three measurements exist between node 2 and node 3, as well as between node 3 and node 4. In addition, a single measurement is present between the non-adjacent nodes 1 and 3, resulting in the pose transformation $T_{13} \in SE(3)$. Likewise, one measurement exists between the non-adjacent nodes 2 and 4, leading to the pose transformation $T_{24} \in SE(3)$. It is assumed that among the measurements between node 3 and node 4, one measurement $T_{34} \in SE(3)$ is an outlier. The objective of the proposed algorithm is to identify and eliminate this outlier.

3. Proposed Method

3.1. Algorithm Overview

In this study, a weighted IQR-based outlier detection algorithm is proposed to identify edges containing outliers in a pose graph. The basic principle of the algorithm is as follows: for any two adjacent nodes i and j , multiple paths are searched using a path-finding algorithm, where the cumulative pose transformation corresponding to each path is defined as $T_{ij} = \prod T_{uv}$, and T_{uv} denotes the pose transformation of each edge along the path. The multiple cumulative pose transformations T_{ij} between nodes i and j are then processed by the weighted IQR algorithm to identify inconsistent outliers, thereby enabling the detection of edges with outliers in the pose graph.

Fig. 2 presents a simplified system block diagram, which serves as an abstraction of the proposed algorithm. The complete algorithmic workflow is provided in Algorithm 1 in Sec. 3.2. The input data of the algorithm consist of a pose graph, and the output corresponds to the edges within the pose graph that contain outliers. The input pose graph is first processed in the "Path Finding" module to search for paths, with algorithmic details described in Sec. 3.5. The paths obtained are subsequently fed into the "Pose Accumulation along the Path" module, where the respective pose transformations T_{ij} of each edge are accumulated. The resulting accumulated transformations T_{ij} are then examined for

outliers in the "Removing Outliers in Translation Vectors" and "Removing Outliers in Rotation Matrices" modules, as detailed in Sec. 3.3 and 3.4, respectively. Finally, the "Path Outlier Removal" module outputs the edges identified as containing outliers.

3.2. Algorithm Details

Let p_1 and p_2 be two nodes in the graph. As illustrated in Fig. 3, three measurements were conducted between p_1 and p_2 , resulting in three pose transformation matrices $T_{12}^1, T_{12}^2, T_{12}^3 \in SE(3)$. As shown in Fig. 4, a connection between p_1 and p_2 can also be established via intermediate nodes such as p_3, p_4 and p_5 . The pose transformation between p_1 and p_2 can thus be represented through intermediate nodes, as expressed in Eq. (1).

$$\begin{aligned} T_{12}^4 &= T_{13}T_{32}, \\ T_{12}^5 &= T_{14}T_{42}, \\ T_{12}^6 &= T_{15}T_{52}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

As shown in Fig. 5, connections between p_1 and p_2 can also be established via two intermediate nodes (e.g., p_6 and p_7 ; p_8 and p_9 ; or p_{10} and p_{11}). As illustrated in Eq. (2), the pose transformation between p_1 and p_2 can be expressed with the aid of two intermediate nodes.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{12}^7 &= T_{16}T_{67}T_{72}, \\ T_{12}^8 &= T_{18}T_{89}T_{92}, \\ T_{12}^9 &= T_{1,10}T_{10,11}T_{11,2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

By extension, the relative transformation between p_1 and p_2 can be represented via multiple intermediate nodes. The identification of such intermediate nodes can be facilitated through various path planning algorithms, such as the Dijkstra algorithm. Assuming this process yields a total of n relative pose transformations between p_1 and p_2 , these transformations are denoted as $T_{12}^i \in SE(3), i \in [1, n]$.

If only regular noise (such as low-variance Gaussian noise) is present in the relative pose transformations between all nodes involved in computing the pose transformation between p_1 and p_2 , then the resulting estimates $T_{12}^i, i \in [1, n]$ are expected to be relatively consistent. In contrast, if outlier noise exists in the pose transformations between certain nodes, some of the computed $T_{12}^i, i \in [1, n]$ will exhibit outlier values.

The preceding analysis outlines the theoretical foundation of the outlier removal algorithm. In the following, the overall procedure of the outlier removal algorithm is introduced. Typically, the input data are represented as a graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, where the nodes \mathcal{V} correspond to keyframes in SLAM or nodes in a sensor network, and the edges \mathcal{E} denote relative pose transformations between different nodes. Each edge $e_{jk} \in \mathcal{E}$ in the graph G must be examined for potential outliers and removed if identified as such. Let $|\mathcal{E}|$ denote the total number of edges in graph G ; consequently, outlier

detection must be performed on all $|\mathcal{E}|$ edges within the graph.

The path planning algorithm (e.g., Dijkstra's algorithm) is employed to identify paths between the two nodes p_j and p_k of edge e_{jk} . If the number of identified paths is insufficient, resulting in a limited number of available pose transformations $T_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n_1]$ (where $n_1 < n_{\text{thres}}$), outlier detection may be omitted. This is because an insufficient number of data points would render the outlier detection results unreliable. The minimum number of paths required to perform outlier detection for each edge $e_{jk} \in \mathcal{E}$ is defined as n_{thres} (with a recommended value of 5). Furthermore, the recommended number of paths to be used for outlier detection on each edge $e_{jk} \in \mathcal{E}$ is denoted by n_{expect} , with a suggested value of 10. Utilizing too few paths may compromise the effectiveness of outlier detection, whereas using an excessive number of paths could increase the computational cost of path searching.

Assuming that a path planning algorithm is employed to find n paths between the two nodes p_j and p_k of edge e_{jk} , the corresponding n relative pose transformations $T_{jk}^i \in \text{SE}(3), i \in [1, n]$, are subsequently computed. Each transformation matrix T_{jk}^i is then decomposed into a rotation matrix $R_{jk}^i \in \text{SO}(3)$ and a translation vector $t_{jk}^i \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Outlier removal is performed independently on the sets of rotation matrices R_{jk}^i and translation vectors t_{jk}^i . A transformation matrix $T_{jk}^i, i = i_1$ is considered an outlier if either its corresponding rotation matrix $R_{jk}^{i_1}$ or translation vector $t_{jk}^{i_1}$ is identified as an outlier. The specific procedures for outlier removal from the sets of rotation matrices $R_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$, and translation vectors $t_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$, are detailed in Algorithms 4, 5, and 6.

Given that there are n relative pose transformations $T_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$ between points p_j and p_k , an outlier transformation $T_{jk}^i, i = i_1$ is identified using the interquartile range (IQR) method. If $T_{jk}^{i_1}$ is derived through multiple edges (e.g., $T_{jk}^{i_1} = T_{jl}^{i_1} T_{lk}^{i_1}$), it is not possible to determine whether any specific edge in this composition is an outlier, or whether the entire path of $T_{jk}^{i_1}$ is free of outliers. The identification of $T_{jk}^{i_1}$ as an outlier may result solely from the accumulation of errors. Conversely, if $T_{jk}^{i_1}$ is obtained through a single edge (i.e., without passing through other nodes), it is considered an outlier.

Furthermore, since the IQR method is employed to identify outliers, it imposes strict assumptions on the data distribution. Specifically, the algorithm presumes the absence of outliers only when the data points are uniformly distributed. To address this limitation, allowable noise range variables $t_{\text{tol}}, \theta_{\text{tol}} \in \mathbb{R}$ are introduced based on the distribution characteristics of normal noise. Given that n pose transformations $T_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$ are obtained between points p_j and p_k , it is assumed that none of these transformations are actual outliers. However, if the transformations are not exactly

uniformly distributed, data points located at the distribution tails may still be erroneously identified as outliers.

To mitigate this, the normal fluctuation range for each component of the translation is defined as $[-t_{\text{noise}}, t_{\text{noise}}]$, and the corresponding allowable noise range is set as $t_{\text{tol}} = c \times t_{\text{noise}}$, where c is recommended to be in the range of 5 to 10. If a translation component $t_{jk}^{i_1}$ of a specific pose transformation $T_{jk}^{i_1}$ is classified as an outlier by the IQR method but falls within the interval $[\text{IQR} - t_{\text{tol}}, \text{IQR} + t_{\text{tol}}]$, it should be considered as normal noise and not treated as an actual outlier. Similarly, for the rotation vector components, the normal fluctuation range is defined as $[-\theta_{\text{noise}}, \theta_{\text{noise}}]$, and the allowable range is set as $\theta_{\text{tol}} = c \times \theta_{\text{noise}}$, with c again recommended to be within the range of 5 to 10. The allowable translation noise range t_{tol} and allowable rotational noise range θ_{tol} are utilized in Algorithm 3.

Outliers between the two nodes p_j and p_k connected by edge e_{jk} have been detected without the involvement of intermediate nodes. The corresponding edges associated with these outliers are subsequently removed from the graph G . This outlier removal process is then applied to the remaining edges $e_{jk} \in \mathcal{E}$, continuing until all edges in the graph have been evaluated and any pose transformations identified as outliers have been eliminated. Outliers detected between nodes p_j and p_k are removed immediately upon identification, rather than waiting for the detection process to be completed for the entire graph. The proposed algorithm requires the identification of multiple paths between adjacent nodes p_j and p_k ; a higher proportion of outliers reduces the reliability of the corresponding pose transformations along these paths. Therefore, immediate removal of detected outliers is necessary to prevent adverse effects on subsequent outlier detection.

At the initial stage of outlier detection for the edge $e_{jk} = (p_j, p_k)$ in the graph G , the number of outliers in G is relatively high, resulting in the poorest detection performance. Conversely, at the final stage of detecting outliers for the edge $e_{jk} = (p_j, p_k)$, the number of outliers is comparatively low, leading to the best detection performance. Therefore, to enhance the effectiveness of outlier removal, it is recommended that two rounds of outlier elimination be applied to graph G . Let the number of outlier removal iterations be denoted by $iter_num$, which is suggested to be set to 2.

In SLAM problems, outlier detection can be performed incrementally. During local optimization, once a sufficient number of edges has been accumulated between any two nodes, the proposed algorithm can be employed to detect and remove outliers. Subsequently, in global optimization, the graph that has already undergone outlier removal during local optimization can be directly utilized, without the need to reapply the detection process to the entire graph. Therefore, the iteration count $iter_num$ pertains only to scenarios where a complete round of outlier detection and removal is performed on the entire graph G , and is not required in typical SLAM applications where full-graph iterative detection is unnecessary. The pseudocode of the pose transformation outlier removal algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Pose Transformation

Input: A graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, where an edge $e_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}$ represents a pose transformation T_{ij} ; the expected number of paths n_{expect} , the path quantity threshold n_{thres} , and the number of iterations $iter_num$

Output: A refined graph $G' = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}']$ with outliers removed

```

1: for  $m \in [1, iter\_num]$  do
2:   for  $e_{jk} \in \mathcal{E}$  do
3:     The path planning algorithm 2 is applied to
     search for  $n_{\text{expect}}$  paths from  $p_j$  to  $p_k$ , resulting in  $n$  actual
     paths denoted as  $\text{Path}[j]$ , where  $j \in [1, n]$ .
4:     if  $n < n_{\text{thres}}$  then
5:       continue
6:     end if
7:     For the  $n$  paths from  $p_j$  to  $p_k$ , the corresponding
     pose transformations  $T_{jk}^i$ ,  $i \in [1, n]$ , are computed.
8:     The outlier removal algorithm for translation
     vectors (Algorithm 4) is employed to identify the set of
     outlier indices  $S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, \text{trans}}$  from the translation components
      $t_{jk}^i$  of  $T_{jk}^i$ .
9:     The outlier removal algorithms for rotation matrices
     (Algorithms 5, 6, 7) are applied to obtain the
     outlier index set  $S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}}$  from the rotational components
      $R_{jk}^i$  of  $T_{jk}^i$ .
10:    The union of outlier indices is computed as
     $S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, T} = S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, \text{trans}} \cup S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}}$ .
11:    for  $i \in S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, T}$  do
12:      if  $\text{len}(\text{Path}[i]) == 1$  then
13:        The edge corresponding to  $\text{Path}[j]$  is re-
        moved from graph  $G$ .
14:      end if
15:    end for
16:  end for
17: end for
18: Return the refined graph  $G' = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}']$  with outliers
    removed.
    
```

3.3. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Translation Vectors

3.3.1. The Weighted Interquartile Range (IQR)

Numerous outlier removal algorithms have been developed, including density-based methods (e.g., DBSCAN Ester, Kriegel, Sander and Xu (1996)), clustering-based methods (e.g., K-means MacQueen (1967)), and distribution-based methods (e.g., the Interquartile Range, IQR). In the this study, it is assumed that the data points are centered around a single cluster center. To reduce computational complexity, the IQR method is selected for outlier removal in this paper. To enhance the applicability of the IQR algorithm to the current problem, a weighted IQR algorithm is proposed as an improvement over the standard approach.

The procedure of the IQR algorithm is briefly introduced as follows. Let the input dataset be denoted as $\mathcal{X} = \{x_i \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$, where n data points x_i are arranged

in ascending order. The first quartile (Q_1), third quartile (Q_3), and the interquartile range (IQR) are subsequently computed. The first quartile Q_1 is determined as follows. When the number of data points n is odd, Q_1 corresponds to the data point at position $0.25(n+1)$, which may be obtained via interpolation. When n is even, Q_1 is calculated as the interpolated value between the data points at positions $0.25n$ and $0.25n+1$. The third quartile Q_3 is computed in a similar manner. For an odd n , Q_3 corresponds to the value at position $0.75(n+1)$; for an even n , it is obtained by interpolating between the data points at positions $0.75n$ and $0.75n+1$. The interquartile range IQR is defined as the difference between Q_3 and Q_1 , as shown in Eq. (3).

$$\text{IQR} = Q_3 - Q_1. \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, the upper and lower bounds for outlier detection are determined based on the interquartile range (IQR). Typically, a constant value of $k = 1.5$ is employed to define the threshold for identifying outliers. The lower bound is calculated using the formula $Q_1 - 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$, while the upper bound is obtained through $Q_3 + 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$. These two thresholds delineate a reasonable range for the data, and any data points falling outside this interval are considered outliers.

Based on the computed bounds, data points in the dataset that are either less than the lower bound or greater than the upper bound are identified as outliers. Specifically, a data point x_i is regarded as a lower outlier if $x_i < Q_1 - 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$, and as an upper outlier if $x_i > Q_3 + 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$. Only data points within the interval $[Q_1 - 1.5 \times \text{IQR}, Q_3 + 1.5 \times \text{IQR}]$ are retained for further analysis.

The advantage of the IQR algorithm lies in its use of quantile-based computation, which makes it robust to outliers and computationally efficient. When applied to the current problem, the data points are denoted as $T_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$. Among these, some T_{jk}^i are directly obtained through measurements, while others are computed as the product of multiple pose transformations. Consequently, the reliability of different T_{jk}^i varies. To address this, a weighted IQR algorithm is proposed.

Let the input data be represented as $\mathcal{X} = \{x_i \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$, where the n data points x_i are sorted in ascending order. The corresponding weight set for the data points \mathbb{X} is denoted as $\mathcal{W} = \{w_i \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$. Here, the weight w_i reflects the reliability of the data point x_i , or alternatively, the probability of x_i being a non-outlier. Typically, this reliability can be determined based on the variance of the sensor used to measure x_i ; lower sensor variance implies higher reliability of the corresponding data point. Therefore, when computing the main data distribution interval (i.e., the IQR range), greater emphasis should be placed on data points with higher reliability.

Compared to the standard IQR algorithm, the weighted IQR algorithm requires modifications in the computation of Q_1 and Q_3 . Specifically, an accumulated weight set $\mathcal{W}_{\text{add}} =$

$\{w_i^{\text{add}} \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$ must be computed, where each element w_i^{add} is calculated according to Eq. (4).

$$w_i^{\text{add}} = \sum_{j=1}^i w_j. \quad (4)$$

The total weight sum W_{sum} is then computed as shown in Eq. (5).

$$W_{\text{sum}} = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j. \quad (5)$$

The first quartile (Q_1) is computed as follows. If there exists a weight $w_{i_1}^{\text{add}}$ in the cumulative weight set \mathcal{W}_{add} such that $w_{i_1}^{\text{add}} = 0.25 \times W_{\text{sum}}$, then $Q_1 = x_{i_1}$. Alternatively, if two consecutive weights $w_{i_1}^{\text{add}}$ and $w_{i_1+1}^{\text{add}}$ in \mathcal{W}_{add} are identified such that $w_{i_1}^{\text{add}} < 0.25 \times W_{\text{sum}} < w_{i_1+1}^{\text{add}}$, then $Q_1 = (x_{i_1} + x_{i_1+1})/2$. The third quartile (Q_3) is calculated analogously. If there exists a weight $w_{i_2}^{\text{add}}$ in \mathcal{W}_{add} satisfying $w_{i_2}^{\text{add}} = 0.75 \times W_{\text{sum}}$, then $Q_3 = x_{i_2}$. Otherwise, if two consecutive weights $w_{i_2}^{\text{add}}$ and $w_{i_2+1}^{\text{add}}$ in \mathcal{W}_{add} meet the condition $w_{i_2}^{\text{add}} < 0.75 \times W_{\text{sum}} < w_{i_2+1}^{\text{add}}$, then $Q_3 = (x_{i_2} + x_{i_2+1})/2$. In other steps, the weighted IQR algorithm follows the same procedure as the standard IQR.

In addition, translational noise tolerance t_{tol} and rotational noise tolerance θ_{tol} are incorporated into the algorithm. A translational data point x_i is not considered an outlier if it falls within the range $[\text{IQR} - t_{\text{tol}}, \text{IQR} + t_{\text{tol}}]$. Similarly, a rotational data point x_j is not regarded as an outlier if it lies within the interval $[\text{IQR} - \theta_{\text{tol}}, \text{IQR} + \theta_{\text{tol}}]$. The pseudocode of the weighted IQR algorithm is presented in Algorithm 3 in Appendix A.

3.3.2. Weight Computation

In the proposed algorithm, a total of n pose transformations T_{jk}^i , where $i \in [1, n]$, are obtained between points p_j and p_k . Some of these transformations T_{jk}^i are directly measured, while others are derived through the composition of multiple pose transformation matrices. Consequently, the reliability of each pose transformation T_{jk}^i varies.

Let the weight of each edge $e_{jk} \in \mathcal{E}$ in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ be denoted as w_{jk} . This weight represents either the prior probability that the corresponding pose transformation T_{jk}^i is not an outlier or the reliability of the transformation T_{jk}^i . The weight w_{jk} can be predefined based on the reliability or variance of the sensor measurements.

Assuming that points p_j and p_k are connected via point p_l , the relative pose transformation between p_j and p_k is given by Eq. (6):

$$T_{jk} = T_{jl}T_{lk}. \quad (6)$$

Let the weight associated with T_{jl} , representing the probability of being an inlier, be denoted as w_{jl} , and similarly, the weight for T_{lk} be w_{lk} . Accordingly, the weight

corresponding to T_{jk} , denoted as w_{jk} , is computed as shown in Eq. (7):

$$w_{jk} = w_{jl}w_{lk}. \quad (7)$$

Under normal circumstances, it is required that both T_{jl} and T_{lk} are inliers in order for the computed transformation T_{jk} to also be an inlier. Accordingly, the probability that T_{jk} is an inlier is given by the product of w_{jl} and w_{lk} . However, there exists a non-zero probability that both T_{jl} and T_{lk} are outliers, yet the resulting T_{jk} appears as an inlier due to coincidence. Conversely, it is also possible that both T_{jl} and T_{lk} are inliers, but the computed T_{jk} turns out to be an outlier. Nevertheless, such cases are typically rare and, for the purpose of computational simplification, their probabilities are neglected. A more general case is considered as follows. Suppose the pose transformation T_{jk}^i is associated with a set of m edges $e_l \in S_{\text{edge}}$, where S_{edge} denotes the collection of these m edges, and each edge e_l has an associated weight w_l . Then, the weight corresponding to the pose transformation T_{jk}^i is given by Eq. 8:

$$w_{jk}^i = \prod_{l \in S_{\text{edge}}} w_l. \quad (8)$$

Following the procedure described above, the weights w_{jk}^i for each of the n pose transformations T_{jk}^i , where $i \in [1, n]$, can be computed accordingly.

3.3.3. Outlier Removal in Translation Vectors

The rotation matrix R_{jk}^i and the translation vector t_{jk}^i in the pose transformation T_{jk}^i are separated, and outliers are removed sequentially. The method for removing outliers from the translation vectors $\{t_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$ is described first. If the entire system operates on a planar surface, the translation vector t_{jk}^i can be expressed as in Eq. (9).

$$t_{jk}^i = \begin{bmatrix} t_{x,jk}^i \\ t_{y,jk}^i \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad i \in [1, n]. \quad (9)$$

For each component of $\{t_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$ – namely, $t_{x,jk}^i$ and $t_{y,jk}^i$ – outliers are identified and removed sequentially using the weighted IQR algorithm. If any component is determined to be an outlier, the entire data point t_{jk}^i is treated as an outlier and discarded accordingly.

If the system operates in three-dimensional space, the translation vector $t_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$ is formulated as shown in Eq. (10).

$$t_{jk}^i = \begin{bmatrix} t_{x,jk}^i \\ t_{y,jk}^i \\ t_{z,jk}^i \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad i \in [1, n]. \quad (10)$$

Outliers are removed from each component of $\mathbf{t}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$ – namely, $t_{x,jk}^i, t_{y,jk}^i$, and $t_{z,jk}^i$ – sequentially using the weighted IQR algorithm. If any single component is identified as an outlier, the entire data point \mathbf{t}_{jk}^i is classified as an outlier and removed accordingly. The pseudocode for the outlier removal process of translation vectors in three-dimensional space is presented in Algorithm 4 in Appendix A.

3.4. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Rotation Matrices

3.4.1. Outlier Removal in 2D Rotation Matrices

If the entire SLAM system operates on a planar surface, the resulting pose transformation matrix \mathbf{T} corresponds to the forms given in Eqs. (11) and (12).

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{t} \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \text{SE}(2). \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \in \text{SO}(2). \quad (12)$$

As shown in Eq. (13), the rotation matrix \mathbf{R} can be converted into a single rotation angle θ .

$$\theta = \arcsin r_{12} \in (-\pi, \pi]. \quad (13)$$

The set of rotation matrices $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$ yields a corresponding set of rotation angles $\{\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$. However, due to the periodic nature of rotation angles, directly applying outlier removal algorithms to the values of θ_i may lead to complications. Specifically, when multiple θ_i values are distributed near π , some angles may be slightly less than π (i.e., numerically close to π), while others may be slightly greater than $-\pi$ (i.e., numerically close to $-\pi$). This discontinuity across the boundary causes angles that are actually close in value to appear numerically distant, thereby introducing significant errors in the outlier detection process.

Accordingly, the following approach is proposed. Given a set of angles denoted as $\{\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$, these angles are first transformed into coordinates on the unit circle, represented as $\{\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{circle}} = [\cos \theta_i, \sin \theta_i]^T, i \in [1, n]\}$. Since it is assumed that the data are centered around a single cluster, the corresponding points on the unit circle are also expected to exhibit a single cluster in the two-dimensional plane.

Subsequently, the two component sets of $\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{circle}}$, namely $C_{\cos} = \{\cos \theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ and $C_{\sin} = \{\sin \theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$, are processed individually using a weighted IQR Algorithm 3 to detect outliers. If either component of a point is identified as an outlier, the corresponding θ_i is considered an outlier. The pseudocode for this algorithm is provided in Algorithm 5 in Appendix A.

By applying Algorithm 5, outliers in the set of rotation matrices $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$ have been detected, resulting in

an outlier index set as $S_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}}$ and an inlier index set as $S_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}} = \{1, \dots, n\} / S_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}}$. However, this algorithm identifies outliers by independently processing the component sets $\{\sin \theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ and $\{\cos \theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$. Since the sine and cosine functions do not exhibit a uniform mapping in the $x - y$ plane, certain data points \mathbf{R}_{jk}^i that are actually outliers may not be removed, while some inliers may be incorrectly classified as outliers and consequently discarded.

In general, the application of Algorithm 5 yields a relatively reliable set of rotation matrices with outliers removed, denoted as $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in S_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}}\}$. However, for scenarios requiring more precise outlier rejection, the following additional steps may be applied.

As shown in Eq. (14), the mean of the inlier rotation angles is computed based on the inlier index set $S_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}}$ obtained from Algorithm 5.

$$\theta_{\text{ave}} = \frac{1}{|S_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}}|} \sum_{i \in S_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}}} \theta_i. \quad (14)$$

As shown in Eq. (15), each angle value in the set $\{\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$ is adjusted to fall within the range $(\theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi, \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi]$.

$$\theta_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} \theta_i, & \text{if } \theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi < \theta_i \leq \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ \theta_i - 2\pi, & \text{if } \theta_i > \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ \theta_i + 2\pi, & \text{if } \theta_i \leq \theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi \end{cases}, \quad i \in [1, n]. \quad (15)$$

Therefore, the purpose of Algorithm 5 is to compute a preliminary set of outlier points, denoted as $S_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D,rot}}$, in order to estimate the principal range of angular concentration (θ_{ave}). Subsequently, using θ_{ave} as the center, all angles $\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]$ are adjusted to fall within the interval $(\theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi, \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi]$. Following this adjustment, the IQR method is applied to the set $\{\theta_i \in (\theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi, \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$ to eliminate outliers. The corresponding pseudocode is presented in Algorithm 6 in Appendix A.

In practical SLAM systems, the computational cost of the algorithm can be further reduced. This is because the rotational angle of the pose transformation between two actual nodes, p_j and p_j , is typically small and concentrated near 0 degrees. Given a set of angles $\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]$, if it is observed that all angle values θ_i fall within the range $[-\theta_{\text{thres}}, \theta_{\text{thres}}]$, it is not necessary to adjust the representation range of θ_i . Instead, the outlier removal can be directly performed using the angles represented within the range $(-\pi, \pi]$. It is recommended to set the parameter θ_{thres} to $2\pi/3$. The pseudocode incorporating this additional verification step is presented in Algorithm 8 in Appendix B.

3.4.2. Outlier Removal in 3D Rotation Matrices

If the entire system operates in three-dimensional space, the pose transformation matrix \mathbf{T} is defined as in Eq. (16).

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{t} \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \text{SE}(3), \mathbf{R} \in \text{SO}(3). \quad (16)$$

As shown in Eq. (17), the rotation matrix \mathbf{R} is converted into a rotation vector \mathbf{v} .

$$\mathbf{v} = h(\mathbf{R}), \mathbf{v} = \theta \mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (17)$$

where the function $h(\cdot)$ maps the rotation matrix \mathbf{R} to the rotation vector \mathbf{v} ; $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes a unit vector representing the axis of rotation; and $\theta \in [0, \pi]$ represents the rotation angle.

Accordingly, the set of n relative pose transformation matrices T_{jk}^i , where $i \in [1, n]$, can be converted into a corresponding set of rotation vectors $\mathcal{V}_{\text{rot}} = \{\mathbf{v}_i = \theta_i \mathbf{n}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3, i \in [1, n], \theta_i \in [0, \pi]\}$. However, due to the periodic nature of rotation angles, directly applying outlier removal algorithms to the set \mathcal{V}_{rot} leads to the following issue. The values of θ_i corresponding to various elements \mathbf{v}_i in \mathcal{V}_{rot} may cluster around π , with some slightly less than π and others slightly greater. As a result, the associated vectors \mathbf{v}_i become distributed in nearly opposite directions. Consequently, rotation matrices T_{jk}^i that are geometrically similar may correspond to rotation vectors \mathbf{v}_i that are significantly distant from each other in three-dimensional space.

The following algorithmic steps are proposed. It is assumed that the rotation matrix T_{jk}^i possesses a single geometric aggregation center. If the rotation angle corresponding to T_{jk}^i deviates significantly from π , the associated rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i exhibits a single cluster center. Conversely, if the rotation angle of T_{jk}^i is close to π , the corresponding rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i presents two cluster centers with opposite directions. In either case, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) can be applied to the set of rotation vectors \mathcal{V}_{rot} to compute the principal direction of the vector distribution, denoted as $\mathbf{n}_{\text{pca}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$.

Since it is not known whether the computed vector \mathbf{n}_{pca} corresponds to the principal direction of the rotation vector set \mathcal{V}_{rot} or to the direction opposite to it, the following approach is adopted for analysis. As shown in Eq. (18), the vector \mathbf{n}_{pca} is normalized to a unit vector.

$$\mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}} = \frac{\mathbf{n}_{\text{pca}}}{\|\mathbf{n}_{\text{pca}}\|}. \quad (18)$$

The direction vector opposite to $\mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$ is defined as $\mathbf{n}_{\text{inverse}} = -\mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$. Let the accumulation variables C_{normal} and C_{inverse} be initialized to zero. For each rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i in the set \mathcal{V}_{rot} , the inner product $\mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$ is computed. Consequently, the set of inner products is obtained as $C = \{c_i = \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}, i \in [1, n]\}$.

For each inner product $c_i = \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$ in the set C , if the inner product is greater than zero, it indicates that the angle between the vector \mathbf{v}_i and $\mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$ is less than $\pi/2$. In this

case, the inner product c_i is accumulated into the variable C_{normal} . Conversely, if the inner product is less than zero, it implies that the angle between \mathbf{v}_i and $\mathbf{n}_{\text{inverse}}$ is less than $\pi/2$; therefore, the negated inner product $-c_i$ is accumulated into the variable C_{inverse} .

If the accumulated variable C_{normal} is greater than C_{inverse} , then $\mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$ is considered the principal direction of the rotation vector set \mathcal{V}_{rot} ; otherwise, $\mathbf{n}_{\text{inverse}}$ is regarded as the principal direction of \mathcal{V}_{rot} . As shown in Eq. (19), the principal direction is denoted by $\mathbf{n}_{\text{main}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$.

$$\mathbf{n}_{\text{main}} \leftarrow \begin{cases} \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}, & \text{if } C_{\text{normal}} \geq C_{\text{inverse}} \\ \mathbf{n}_{\text{inverse}}, & \text{if } C_{\text{normal}} < C_{\text{inverse}} \end{cases}. \quad (19)$$

As shown in Eq. (20), if $\mathbf{n}_{\text{inverse}}$ is the principal direction of the rotation vector set \mathcal{V}_{rot} , denoted as \mathbf{n}_{main} , and the condition $C_{\text{normal}} < C_{\text{inverse}}$ holds, then each value in the inner product set $C = \{c_i = \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}, i \in [1, n]\}$ is multiplied by -1 .

$$c_i \leftarrow -c_i, i \in [1, n], \quad \text{if } C_{\text{normal}} < C_{\text{inverse}}. \quad (20)$$

At this stage, the principal direction \mathbf{n}_{main} (a unit vector) of the set of rotation vectors \mathcal{V}_{rot} has been obtained. Additionally, the set C , consisting of the inner products between each rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i and the principal direction \mathbf{n}_{main} , has been derived. Since \mathbf{n}_{main} is a unit vector, each element c_i in C can be interpreted as the projection length of the rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i onto the principal direction \mathbf{n}_{main} . Moreover, given that the norm of the rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i represents the rotation angle, the projection length $c_i \in (-\pi, \pi]$ corresponds to the rotation angle of \mathbf{v}_i along the principal direction.

A similar issue arises as in the case of outlier detection for two-dimensional rotation matrices, namely the periodicity of rotation angles. To address this, the same approach is adopted: given the set of rotation angles C , corresponding sets of trigonometric functions C_{sin} and C_{cos} are defined. Subsequently, the weighted IQR algorithm is applied separately to C_{sin} and C_{cos} for outlier detection. In this manner, the principal range of the distribution of elements in the projected rotation angle set C is determined. The detailed procedure is as follows.

The set of projection lengths $C = \{c_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$ of the rotation vector set \mathcal{V}_{rot} onto the principal direction \mathbf{n}_{main} has been obtained. These projection lengths $c_i \in (-\pi, \pi]$ represent the rotational angles of the vectors \mathbf{v}_i projected along the principal direction. However, due to the periodic nature of rotational angles, directly applying outlier detection algorithms to the set C may lead to the following issue. When multiple values of c_i are distributed near π , some of them may be slightly less than π (i.e., values close to π), while others may be slightly greater than $-\pi$ (i.e., values close to $-\pi$). Since these angle values span the discontinuity boundary, angles that are actually close in magnitude can appear to differ significantly in numerical value.

Accordingly, the following method is proposed. Given a set of angles defined as $C = \{c_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$, these

angles are first transformed into coordinates on the unit circle as $\{p_i^{\text{circle}} = [\cos c_i, \sin c_i]^T, i \in [1, n]\}$. Since it is assumed that the data exhibit a single cluster center, the corresponding coordinates on the unit circle are also expected to form a single cluster in the two-dimensional plane. Subsequently, the two components of each p_i^{circle} (i.e., $\cos c_i$ and $\sin c_i$) are individually subjected to the weighted IQR algorithm to identify outliers. If either component is identified as an outlier, the corresponding c_i is classified as an outlier.

The weighted IQR algorithm is applied to the set $C_{\cos} = \{\cos c_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ to obtain the outlier index set $S_{\text{outlier}}^{\cos}$. Similarly, the same algorithm is applied to the set $C_{\sin} = \{\sin c_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ to derive the outlier index set $S_{\text{outlier}}^{\sin}$. Let the union of outlier index sets $S_{\text{outlier}}^{\cos}$ and $S_{\text{outlier}}^{\sin}$ be denoted as $S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}, \text{rough}} = S_{\text{outlier}}^{\cos} \cup S_{\text{outlier}}^{\sin}$. The set $S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}, \text{rough}}$ thus represents the indices of outlier elements obtained through the coarse detection of outliers from both C_{\sin} and C_{\cos} . The inlier index set is defined as $S_{\text{inlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}, \text{rough}} = [1, \dots, n] / S_{\text{outlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}, \text{rough}}$. The mean value of the non-outlier c_i is then computed as shown in Eq. (21).

$$c_{\text{ave}} = \frac{1}{|S_{\text{inlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}, \text{rough}}|} \sum_{i \in S_{\text{inlier}}^{3D, \text{rot}, \text{rough}}} c_i. \quad (21)$$

In the algorithm for outlier detection in two-dimensional rotation matrices, after computing the mean of the inlier angles, denoted as c_{ave} , each angle in the set $C = \{c_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$ is adjusted to lie within the interval $(c_{\text{ave}} - \pi, c_{\text{ave}} + \pi]$. However, for the outlier detection algorithm involving three-dimensional rotation matrices, the objective is to modify the set of rotation vectors \mathcal{V}_{rot} . If an element c_i in the angle set C lies within the interval $(c_{\text{ave}} - \pi, c_{\text{ave}} + \pi]$, the corresponding rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i remains unchanged. If $c_i > c_{\text{ave}} + \pi$, the rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i is reversed in direction, and its magnitude is adjusted to $2\pi - \|\mathbf{v}_i\|$. Similarly, if $c_i \leq c_{\text{ave}} - \pi$, the direction of \mathbf{v}_i is also reversed, and its magnitude is modified to $2\pi - \|\mathbf{v}_i\|$. The procedure for processing the rotation vector \mathbf{v}_i is defined in Eq. (22).

$$\mathbf{v}_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} \mathbf{v}_i, & \text{if } c_{\text{ave}} - \pi < c_i \leq c_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ (2\pi - \|\mathbf{v}_i\|) \frac{-\mathbf{v}_i}{\|\mathbf{v}_i\|}, & \text{if } c_i > c_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ (2\pi - \|\mathbf{v}_i\|) \frac{-\mathbf{v}_i}{\|\mathbf{v}_i\|}, & \text{if } c_i \leq c_{\text{ave}} - \pi \end{cases}, \quad i \in [1, n]. \quad (22)$$

After the aforementioned adjustment, each element \mathbf{v}_i in the updated set of rotation vectors \mathcal{V}_{rot} has a projection c_i onto the principal direction \mathbf{n}_{main} that lies within the interval $(c_{\text{ave}} - \pi, c_{\text{ave}} + \pi]$. Furthermore, the majority of the rotation vectors \mathbf{v}_i are concentrated around $c_{\text{ave}} \mathbf{n}_{\text{main}}$, rather than being distributed near the angular discontinuity boundaries.

Subsequently, each component of the rotation vectors \mathbf{v}_i , $i \in [1, n]$ – namely, v_i^1 , v_i^2 , and v_i^3 – is individually processed

using a weighted IQR algorithm to detect outliers. If any component is identified as an outlier, the corresponding rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_{jk}^i is considered an outlier. The pseudocode for the outlier detection process of rotation matrices in three-dimensional space is provided in Algorithm 7 in Appendix A.

In practical SLAM systems, the computational cost of the algorithm can be further reduced. This is due to the fact that the rotational transformation between two actual nodes, p_j, p_j , is typically very small, with the rotation vectors distributed near the origin. Given the set of rotation vectors as $\mathcal{V}_{\text{rot}} = \{\mathbf{v}_i = \theta_i \mathbf{n}_i \in \mathcal{R}^3, i \in [1, n], \theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi]\}$, the corresponding set of vector magnitudes can be computed as $\rho_{\text{rot}} = \{\rho_i = \|\mathbf{v}_i\|, i \in [1, n]\}$. If it is observed that all magnitudes ρ_i lie within the interval $[0, \rho_{\text{thres}}]$, the representation range of the rotation vectors \mathbf{v}_i can remain unchanged. The recommended value for the parameter ρ_{thres} is $2\pi/3$. The pseudocode incorporating this decision step is provided in Algorithm 9 in Appendix B.

3.5. Path Planning Algorithms

3.5.1. Dijkstra's Algorithm

The algorithm aims to identify multiple pose transformations $\mathbf{T}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$ between points p_j and p_k . This problem can be formulated as finding multiple paths from p_j to p_k , for which Dijkstra's algorithm can be employed. Unlike heuristic-based methods, Dijkstra's algorithm does not incorporate directional guidance from a heuristic function during path search. Instead, it initiates from point p_j and expands outward, computing the shortest path cost to each neighboring node until point p_k is reached. However, in this algorithmic context, it is typically required that the connection between p_j and p_k passes through at most one or two intermediate points. If the connection between p_j and p_k involves too many intermediate nodes, the accumulated pose transformation may become inaccurate due to the propagation of noise. Therefore, although Dijkstra's algorithm lacks a heuristic function to guide the search direction, the additional computational cost remains limited when only short paths are considered.

Let the weight of each edge e_{jk} in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ be denoted as w_{jk} ; this weight represents either the probability that the corresponding pose transformation \mathbf{T}_{jk} is a non-outlier or the reliability of the transformation \mathbf{T}_{jk} . The weight w_{jk} can be predetermined based on the reliability or variance of the measuring sensor.

Assuming that points p_j and p_k are connected via an intermediate point p_l , the pose transformation between p_j and p_k is given by Eq. (23).

$$\mathbf{T}_{jk} = \mathbf{T}_{jl} \mathbf{T}_{lk}. \quad (23)$$

Let the weight corresponding to \mathbf{T}_{jl} be denoted as w_{jl} (the probability of being a non-outlier), and the weight corresponding to \mathbf{T}_{lk} as w_{lk} . Then, the probability that \mathbf{T}_{jk} is a non-outlier, denoted as w_{jk} , is given in Eq. (24).

$$w_{jk} = w_{jl}w_{lk}. \quad (24)$$

The objective is to identify a path from p_j to p_k that maximizes the accumulated weight, i.e., the probability of being a non-outlier. However, the error in the above form is not directly applicable to path planning algorithms, as Dijkstra's algorithm requires the path cost to be additive. Therefore, a logarithmic transformation followed by multiplication by -1 is applied to the above error, as shown in Eq. (25).

$$-\log w_{jk} = -\log w_{jl}w_{lk}, \quad -\log w_{jk} = -\log w_{jl} - \log w_{lk}. \quad (25)$$

The weight of each edge, denoted as w_{jk} , is transformed by taking the negative logarithm, resulting in a new weight of $-\log w_{jk}$ for use in the path planning algorithm. This transformation is appropriate because it preserves the additive property required for path cost computation. Prior to applying the negative logarithm, the objective is to identify the path with the maximum total weight, w_{jk} . After the transformation, the problem becomes one of minimizing $-\log w_{jk}$, which aligns with the shortest path formulation commonly employed in path planning algorithms. Furthermore, since the original edge weights satisfy $w_{jk} \in [0, 1]$, the transformed weights satisfy $-\log w_{jk} \in [0, +\infty)$, thereby meeting Dijkstra's algorithm requirement that edge weights be non-negative.

In this algorithm, it is necessary to identify n paths from p_j to p_k such that the lengths (or path costs) of these paths are minimized. Moreover, these paths should avoid using overlapping edges as much as possible. The rationale for minimizing edge repetition is that if a significant number of edges are shared between two paths, the corresponding pose transformations between p_j and p_k lack independence. Consequently, such paths cannot effectively represent two independent measurements of the pose transformation between p_j and p_k .

The following approach can be employed to obtain n distinct paths: First, Dijkstra's algorithm is applied to identify the shortest path from p_j to p_k in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$. Subsequently, the weights of all edges along this path are set to a large constant value Δ (e.g., 10^5), while the weights of all other edges remain unchanged. Dijkstra's algorithm is then executed again to determine a new shortest path from p_j to p_k . Under this modification, the path planning algorithm is encouraged to avoid previously used edges due to their high cost Δ , unless such edges are essential to ensure connectivity from p_j to p_k . This process is repeated iteratively: upon identifying each new path, the weights of its constituent edges are updated to Δ . The algorithm terminates either when n such paths have been found or when the newly identified path consists entirely of previously used edges (i.e., the total path cost equals $k \times \Delta$, where k denotes the number of edges in the path). The pseudocode of the proposed algorithm is provided in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2. Finding Multiple Paths Using Dijkstra's Algorithm

Input: Graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$, edge weight set $\{w_i, i \in [1, |\mathcal{E}|]\}$, maximum number of paths n , path endpoint p_j, p_k
Output: The valid path set $\{\text{Path}[p], p \in [1, q], q \leq n\}$

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ to $|\mathcal{E}|$ **do**
- 2: Compute negative logarithmic weights: $\omega_i \leftarrow -\log w_i$.
- 3: **end for**
- 4: **for** $j = 1$ to n **do**
- 5: Execute the Dijkstra algorithm using ω_i as edge weights to compute the shortest path from p_j to p_k .
- 6: Record the path cost: $C[j] \leftarrow$ cost of shortest path.
- 7: Store the path: $\text{Path}[j] \leftarrow$ shortest path from p_j to p_k .
- 8: **for** each edge e in $\text{Path}[j]$ **do**
- 9: Set its weight to $\Delta(10^5)$.
- 10: **end for**
- 11: **if** $\text{len}(\text{Path}[j]) \times \Delta = C[j]$ **then**
- 12: The valid path number is $p = j - 1$, remove $\text{Path}[j]$.
- 13: **break.**
- 14: **end if**
- 15: **end for**
- 16: Return the valid path set $\{\text{Path}[p], p \in [1, q], q \leq n\}$.

3.5.2. A* Algorithm

The algorithm requires the identification of multiple pose transformations $T_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]$ between points p_j and p_k . This problem is equivalent to finding multiple paths from p_j to p_k . In addition to employing the Dijkstra algorithm, the A* algorithm can also be utilized. The A* algorithm evaluates each node along the path using the objective function defined in Eq. (26).

$$f(n) = g(n) + h(n), \quad (26)$$

where $f(n)$ denotes the total estimated cost from the start point p_j to the goal point p_k ; $g(n)$ represents the actual cost incurred from the start point p_j to the current node n , calculated as the sum of the weights of the traversed edges; $h(n)$ is the heuristic function used to estimate the cost from node n to the goal point p_k . The function $h(n)$ provides directional guidance toward the goal, thereby enabling the algorithm to reach p_k more efficiently. In the absence of the heuristic function $h(n)$, the A* algorithm degenerates into Dijkstra's algorithm.

As shown in Eq. (27), the heuristic function $h(n)$ in the A* algorithm can be implemented using the Euclidean distance.

$$h(n) = \lambda \sqrt{(x_n - x_{pk})^2 + (y_n - y_{pk})^2}. \quad (27)$$

The heuristic function requires prior knowledge of the three-dimensional coordinates of each node in the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$. These coordinates can be initially estimated using the graph $G = [\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}]$ without outlier removal to obtain a coarse

approximation for each node, which is then used in the heuristic function. According to the admissibility condition in the A* algorithm, the heuristic function $h(n)$ must not overestimate the true cost $h^*(n)$; otherwise, the resulting path may be suboptimal. Since the node coordinates are coarsely estimated from the original graph without outlier removal, directly applying the Euclidean distance may lead to $h(n) > h^*(n)$. To address this, the Euclidean distance is scaled by a factor $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. In the A* algorithm, except for the use of the heuristic function, all other steps for finding a path from p_j to p_k are identical to those in the Dijkstra algorithm.

4. Experimental Results and Analysis

4.1. Analysis of Computational Efficiency

Outlier removal in pose transformation plays a significant role in the back-end optimization of SLAM problems. Among existing approaches, methods based on graph theory and Maximal Consensus exhibit similarities to the algorithm proposed in this study. However, such methods are seldom applied in practical scenarios of SLAM back-end optimization and loop closure detection. Instead, various robust kernel function-based algorithms are more commonly employed. This limited adoption is primarily attributed to the high computational complexity of conventional graph-theoretic and Maximal Consensus-based algorithms, particularly when dealing with large-scale graphs.

Taking the algorithm proposed in Mangelson et al. (2018) as an example, the method first identifies loop closures using various techniques (e.g., a loop closure is formed between node i and node j). Subsequently, a consistency matrix $C \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is constructed, where N denotes the number of nodes in the graph. Given a detected loop closure between nodes i and j , the corresponding element c_{ij} in the consistency matrix C is incremented by 1. The elements of C are gradually accumulated based on the detected loop closure edges. Finally, the maximal consistent subset within the matrix C is identified, with its elements corresponding to non-outlier measurements.

Conventional algorithms based on graph theory and maximum consensus typically remove outliers by identifying the maximum consensus set on a graph, which involves substantial computational complexity. In contrast, the proposed algorithm does not adopt this approach; instead, it utilizes the quartile method to eliminate outliers across different pose transformations, thereby significantly reducing the computational load.

In addition, the proposed algorithm identifies multiple pose transformations between any two nodes (e.g., node i and node j), followed by the removal of outlier transformations. This approach is scalable, as it does not require reprocessing the entire graph; instead, it focuses solely on the pose transformations between the selected node pair. Therefore, in the local optimization phase of the SLAM problem, outlier pose transformations can be removed each time a new

transformation is added, and the results of previous outlier detections can be reused during global optimization.

The proposed outlier removal algorithm was implemented using Python. The graph was represented with the NetworkX library, and the Dijkstra function provided by this library was employed to identify paths within the graph. The PCA component of the algorithm was implemented using the scikit-learn library, whereas the weighted IQR algorithm was implemented manually in Python. Due to the substantial engineering effort required for performance optimization via C++ implementation, only a Python version of the algorithm has been developed at this stage. The computational efficiency of the algorithm has been analyzed theoretically, without empirical assessment of execution time.

4.2. Experimental Design

4.2.1. Design of Outlier Detection

Random graphs were generated using the NetworkX library. The variable *num_nodes* denotes the number of nodes, which was set to 30, while *edge_density* represents the probability of an edge existing between any two nodes, with values set to 20% and 40%, respectively. The node poses were randomly generated, where each translation component was sampled from a uniform distribution $U(-5, 5)$, and the rotation matrices were generated randomly. Based on the node poses, the relative poses of the edges were computed, and standard noise was subsequently added to these edge poses. The noise perturbation applied to the edge poses was defined such that each translation component followed a uniform distribution $U(-0.01, 0.01)$, and the norm of the rotation vector was drawn from a uniform distribution $U(-\pi/360, \pi/360)$. Let *outlier_num* denote the number of outliers. A total of *outlier_num* edges were randomly selected from the graph, and outlier noise was added to their relative poses. The outlier perturbation was characterized by translation components sampled from a uniform distribution $U(-10, 10)$, and the norm of the rotation vector followed a uniform distribution $U(-\pi/4, \pi/4)$.

In this experiment, the edge ratio of outlier noise was used as a varying parameter to evaluate the trajectory accuracy of different algorithms under varying proportions of outliers. The outlier ratios were set to 2%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%. The algorithm parameters used in this experiment were configured as follows: translation tolerance $t_{\text{tol}} = 10 \times 0.1$, rotation tolerance $\theta_{\text{tol}} = 10 \times \pi/360$, path count threshold $n_{\text{thres}} = 5$, expected number of paths $n_{\text{expect}} = 10$, and number of iterations *iter_num* = 2.

4.2.2. Design of GTSAM Experiment

Some outlier removal algorithms do not directly identify which data points are outliers; instead, they incorporate a certain proportion of outliers within the optimization problem and still yield correct optimization results. Robust kernel functions, for example, belong to this category of methods. In contrast, the proposed outlier removal algorithm is capable of explicitly identifying which data points are outliers. Therefore, the proposed method can also be applied to optimization problems involving outliers.

Metric/ratio	2%	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%	Metric/ratio	2%	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%
Precision	0.997	0.989	0.995	0.994	0.999	0.998	0.996	Precision	0.984	0.992	0.996	0.997	0.999	0.997	0.998
Recall	0.996	0.992	0.996	0.992	0.985	0.966	0.918	Recall	1	1	1	1	0.998	0.993	0.973
F1-Score	0.996	0.99	0.995	0.993	0.991	0.981	0.955	F1-Score	0.991	0.996	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.995	0.985
Accuracy	1	0.999	0.999	0.998	0.996	0.99	0.971	Accuracy	1	1	1	1	0.999	0.997	0.99

Note: the horizontal axis represents the proportion of outliers.

Table 1

Outlier detection results (edge density = 20%)

The proposed outlier removal algorithm is compared with the graph optimization algorithm provided by the GTSAM library. In the comparison, the graph optimization algorithm is implemented using various types of robust kernel functions, including the Huber, Tukey, Cauchy, Geman-McClure, Fair, and Welsch kernels. The parameters of these kernel functions are set to recommended values: the parameter k is set to 1.345 for the Huber kernel, 4.6851 for the Tukey kernel, and 1.0 for the Cauchy, Geman-McClure, Fair, and Welsch kernels, respectively. The proposed algorithm is employed to remove the outlier in pose transformations. Subsequently, the optimized trajectory is computed using the graph optimization algorithm in the GTSAM library without incorporating any robust kernel function. The accuracy of the optimized trajectory obtained using the proposed method is then compared with the accuracy of trajectories optimized using various robust kernel functions. A higher trajectory accuracy indicates a more effective outlier removal performance.

Random trajectories were generated using the NetworkX library. The number of nodes, denoted as $node_num$, was set to 30, and the edge density, $edge_density$, was specified as 20%. All other parameters were configured identically to those used in the previous experiment. The randomly generated trajectories served as the ground truth. Subsequently, noise was added to these trajectories to produce the input data for the optimization algorithm.

In this experiment, the proportion of edges affected by outlier noise was used as a variable parameter to evaluate the trajectory accuracy of different algorithms under varying levels of outlier contamination. The outlier ratios were set to 2%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%. For each optimization result, the output was saved to a file and subsequently analyzed using the evo tool to compute the RMSE values of APE and RPE metrics. Each experiment corresponding to a specific outlier ratio was repeated fifty times, and the average of these fifty runs was taken as the representative APE and RPE value for that ratio.

4.3. Experimental Results

4.3.1. Results of Outlier Detection

Fig. 6 presents the Precision and Recall curves of the outlier detection algorithms under an edge density of 20%, as the proportion of outliers varies. Tab. 1 reports additional performance metrics of the outlier detection algorithms under the same edge density (20%), including Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and Accuracy.

Table 2

Outlier detection results (edge density = 40%)

Alg./ratio	2%	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%
Huber	0.005	0.006	0.006	0.007	0.02	0.076	0.063
Fair	0.005	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.01	0.058	0.082
myalg	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.022	0.026	0.282

Table 3

APE values for selected algorithms

Alg./ratio	2%	5%	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%
Huber	0.01	0.01	0.011	0.012	0.033	0.117	0.087
Fair	0.01	0.01	0.012	0.012	0.017	0.093	0.126
myalg	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.026	0.039	0.363

Table 4

RPE values for selected algorithms

Fig. 7 illustrates the Precision and Recall curves of the outlier detection algorithms when the edge density is 40%, with varying proportions of outliers. Tab. 2 provides further metric data of the outlier detection algorithms under the edge density of 40%, including Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and Accuracy.

4.3.2. Results of GTSAM Experiment

The detailed experimental results are presented in Figs. 8 and 9.

Fig. 8 illustrates the variations in APE values of the Huber algorithm, the Fair algorithm, and the proposed algorithm with respect to different outlier ratios, while Tab. 3 presents the corresponding numerical results of APE for these algorithms.

Fig. 9 depicts the variations in RPE values of the Huber algorithm, the Fair algorithm, and the proposed algorithm as the outlier ratio changes, and Tab. 4 provides the detailed RPE values for these algorithms.

4.4. Discussion

4.4.1. Discussion of Outlier Detection

In the SLAM problem, greater emphasis is placed on the recall of outlier rejection algorithms. If the recall does not approach 100%, some outliers remain undetected and are incorrectly treated as inliers in the trajectory optimization process, which can lead to significant deviations in the optimized trajectory. In contrast, the precision of the outlier rejection algorithm is relatively less critical, although a higher value is still desirable. If the precision does not reach near-perfect levels, some inliers may be mistakenly removed as outliers. However, since SLAM typically operates with redundant observations beyond what is strictly necessary for

computation, the loss of a portion of these measurements has a limited impact on trajectory optimization.

As shown in Fig. 6, the outlier detection results at an edge density of 20% are presented, including the corresponding Precision and Recall metrics. When the proportion of outliers is below 15%, the algorithm achieves a Recall close to 100%, although not exactly reaching it. However, once the outlier proportion exceeds 15%, a rapid decline in Recall is observed. Fig. 7 illustrates the outlier detection results at an edge density of 40%. In this case, when the proportion of outliers is below 15%, the algorithm consistently achieves a Recall of approximately 100%. As the outlier proportion surpasses 15%, a decrease in Recall is still observed. By comparing these results with those obtained at an edge density of 20%, it can be concluded that a higher edge density leads to improved performance of the outlier removal algorithm.

4.4.2. Discussion of GTSAM Experiment

As shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, the APE and RPE values obtained using the proposed algorithm, as well as the Huber and Fair robust kernel functions, are presented. Other robust kernel functions exhibit high sensitivity to parameter settings, and their default parameters do not yield satisfactory optimization results; therefore, they are not included in this comparison. When the proportion of outliers is below 15%, the optimization performance of the proposed algorithm is comparable to that of the Huber and Fair robust kernel functions. However, when the outlier proportion reaches 30%, the proposed algorithm demonstrates inferior performance relative to the Huber and Fair functions. This degradation is attributed to the fact that, under a high outlier ratio, the recall of the proposed outlier removal algorithm does not approach 100%, resulting in the inclusion of some outliers in the trajectory optimization process and consequently leading to reduced optimization accuracy.

5. Conclusion

This paper presents a lightweight and effective outlier removal algorithm for pose transformation in SLAM and pose graph optimization frameworks. By employing the interquartile range (IQR) and its weighted variant to identify abnormal transformations in both translation and rotation components, the method provides a robust preprocessing step that enhances the reliability of back-end optimization. The results demonstrate that the proposed approach effectively filters out erroneous pose constraints and can be integrated into various SLAM pipelines to improve loop closure consistency. Future work will focus on implementing the method in C++ and validating its performance in real-world robotic applications.

A. Algorithm A

Algorithm 3. The Weighted IQR Algorithm

- 1: **Input:** Dataset $\mathcal{X} = \{x_i \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$, weight set $\mathcal{W} = \{w_i \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$, the allowable translation

noise range t_{tol} (or the allowable rotational noise range θ_{tol})

- 2: **Output:** The outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}$
- 3: Initialize the cumulative weight set: $\mathcal{W}_{\text{add}} = \{w_i^{\text{add}} \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$.
- 4: **for** $i = 1$ to n **do**
- 5: $w_i^{\text{add}} \leftarrow \sum_{j=1}^i w_j$.
- 6: **end for**
- 7: Compute the total weight: $W_{\text{sum}} \leftarrow \sum_{j=1}^n w_j$.
- 8: **for** $i = 1$ to n **do**
- 9: **if** $w_i^{\text{add}} = 0.25 \times W_{\text{sum}}$ **then**
- 10: $Q_1 \leftarrow x_i$.
- 11: **else if** $w_i^{\text{add}} < 0.25 \times W_{\text{sum}}$ **and** $w_{i+1}^{\text{add}} > 0.25 \times W_{\text{sum}}$ **then**
- 12: $Q_1 \leftarrow \frac{x_i + x_{i+1}}{2}$.
- 13: **end if**
- 14: **end for**
- 15: **for** $i = 1$ to n **do**
- 16: **if** $w_i^{\text{add}} = 0.75 \times W_{\text{sum}}$ **then**
- 17: $Q_3 \leftarrow x_i$.
- 18: **else if** $w_i^{\text{add}} < 0.75 \times W_{\text{sum}}$ **and** $w_{i+1}^{\text{add}} > 0.75 \times W_{\text{sum}}$ **then**
- 19: $Q_3 \leftarrow \frac{x_i + x_{i+1}}{2}$.
- 20: **end if**
- 21: **end for**
- 22: Compute the interquartile range (IQR): $\text{IQR} \leftarrow Q_3 - Q_1$
- 23: **for** $x_i \in \mathcal{X}$ **do**
- 24: **if** $x_i \leq Q_1 - 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ **or** $x_i \geq Q_3 + 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ **then**
- 25: **if** $x_i \leq \text{IQR} - t_{\text{tol}}$ **or** $x_i \geq \text{IQR} + t_{\text{tol}}$ **then**
- 26: Add index i to outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}$.
- 27: **end if**
- 28: **end if**
- 29: **end for**
- 30: Return the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}$.

Algorithm 4. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Translation Vectors in 3D Space

- 1: **Input:** Translation set $\mathcal{T} = \left\{ t_{jk}^i = \begin{bmatrix} t_{x,jk}^i \\ t_{y,jk}^i \\ t_{z,jk}^i \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^3, i \in [1, n] \right\}$, weight set $\mathcal{W} = \{w_{jk}^i \in \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, n]\}$
- 2: **Output:** Outlier index set: $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{3\text{D,trans}}$.
- 3: Perform outlier detection using the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 on the $t_{x,jk}^i$ components for $i \in [1, n]$ to obtain outlier index set \mathcal{S}_1 .
- 4: Perform outlier detection using the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 on the $t_{y,jk}^i$ components for $i \in [1, n]$ to obtain outlier index set \mathcal{S}_2 .
- 5: Perform outlier detection using the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 on the $t_{z,jk}^i$ components for $i \in [1, n]$ to obtain outlier index set \mathcal{S}_3 .
- 6: Compute the outlier index set as $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{3\text{D,trans}} = \mathcal{S}_1 \cup \mathcal{S}_2 \cup \mathcal{S}_3$.
- 7: Return the outlier index set: $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{3\text{D,trans}}$.

Algorithm 5. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Rotation Matrices in 2D Space

Input: A set of rotation matrices $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, weights set $\{w_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$

Output: Outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}}$

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ to n **do**
- 2: Compute $\theta_i = \arcsin\left((\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i)_{1,2}\right)$, where $\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi]$.
- 3: Compute the unit circle coordinates $\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{circle}} = [\cos \theta_i, \sin \theta_i]$
- 4: **end for**
- 5: Apply the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 to the set $C_{\cos} = \{\cos \theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ to obtain the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_1 .
- 6: Apply the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 to the set $C_{\sin} = \{\sin \theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ to obtain the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_2 .
- 7: Determine the outlier index set as $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}} = \mathcal{S}_1 \cup \mathcal{S}_2$.
- 8: Return the outlier index set as $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}}$.

Algorithm 6. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Rotation Matrices in 2D Space (Refined Version)

Input: A set of rotation matrices $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, a corresponding set of weights $\{w_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, and an initial outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}}$

Output: The outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot},\text{precise}}$

- 1: Compute $\theta_i = \arcsin\left((\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i)_{1,2}\right)$ for each $i \in [1, n]$, where $\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi]$.
- 2: The inlier index set is defined as $\mathcal{S}_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}} = \{1, \dots, n\} / \mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}}$.
- 3: Compute the average angle over the initial inlier set:

$$\theta_{\text{ave}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{inlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot}}} \theta_i.$$
- 4: Adjust the angle set $\{\theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ to the interval $(\theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi, \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi]$.
- 5:
$$\theta_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} \theta_i, & \text{if } \theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi < \theta_i \leq \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ \theta_i - \pi, & \text{if } \theta_i > \theta_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ \theta_i + \pi, & \text{if } \theta_i \leq \theta_{\text{ave}} - \pi \end{cases}, \quad i \in [1, n].$$
- 6: Apply the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 to the adjusted angle set $\{\theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ to detect outliers, yielding the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot},\text{precise}}$.
- 7: Return the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{2\text{D},\text{rot},\text{precise}}$.

Algorithm 7. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Rotation Matrices in 3D Space

Input: A set of rotation matrices $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, and a corresponding set of weights $\{w_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$

Output: The outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{3\text{D},\text{rot}}$

- 1: Convert each rotation matrix into a rotation vector to obtain the set $\mathcal{V}_{\text{rot}} = \{\mathbf{v}_i = \theta_i \mathbf{n}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3, i \in [1, n], \theta_i \in [0, \pi]\}$.
- 2: Perform Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the set \mathcal{V}_{rot} to compute the principal direction $\mathbf{n}_{\text{pca}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$.
- 3: Normalize the vector \mathbf{n}_{pca} to obtain the unit vector $\mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}} = \mathbf{n}_{\text{pca}} / \|\mathbf{n}_{\text{pca}}\|$.
- 4: Define its opposite vector as $\mathbf{n}_{\text{inverse}} = -\mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$.
- 5: Initialize accumulation variables: $C_{\text{normal}} = 0, C_{\text{inverse}} = 0$.
- 6: **for all** $i \in [1, n]$ **do**

7: Compute the inner product $c_i = \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}$, and add c_i to the inner product set C .

8: **if** $c_i > 0$ **then**

9: $C_{\text{normal}} \leftarrow C_{\text{normal}} + c_i$.

10: **end if**

11: **if** $c_i < 0$ **then**

12: $C_{\text{inverse}} \leftarrow C_{\text{inverse}} - c_i$.

13: **end if**

14: **end for**

15: The principal direction of rotation vector set \mathcal{V}_{rot} is \mathbf{n}_{main} ,

16:

$$\mathbf{n}_{\text{main}} \leftarrow \begin{cases} \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}, & \text{if } C_{\text{normal}} \geq C_{\text{inverse}} \\ \mathbf{n}_{\text{inverse}}, & \text{if } C_{\text{normal}} < C_{\text{inverse}} \end{cases}$$

17: **if** $C_{\text{normal}} < C_{\text{inverse}}$ **then**

18: Multiply each element in the inner product set $C = \{c_i = \mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\text{normal}}, i \in [1, n]\}$ by -1 , i.e., $c_i \leftarrow -c_i, i \in [1, n]$.

19: **end if**

20: Given the inner product set $C = \{c_i \in (-\pi, \pi], i \in [1, n]\}$, compute the sets $C_{\text{sin}} = \{\sin c_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ and $C_{\text{cos}} = \{\cos c_i, i \in [1, n]\}$.

21: Apply the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 to the set C_{sin} to obtain the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{sin}}$.

22: Apply the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 to the set C_{cos} to obtain the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{cos}}$.

23: Compute the union of the index sets: $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{3\text{D},\text{rot},\text{rough}} = \mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{sin}} \cup \mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{cos}}$.

24: The inlier index set is defined as $\mathcal{S}_{\text{inlier}}^{3\text{D},\text{rot},\text{rough}} = \{1, \dots, n\} / \mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{3\text{D},\text{rot},\text{rough}}$

25: Calculate the mean of the non-outlier elements in the set C : $c_{\text{ave}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_{\text{inlier}}^{3\text{D},\text{rot},\text{rough}}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{inlier}}^{3\text{D},\text{rot},\text{rough}}} c_i$.

26: **for all** $i \in [1, n]$ **do**

27: Each element \mathbf{v}_i in the rotation vector set \mathcal{V}_{rot} is adjusted accordingly,

28:

$$\mathbf{v}_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} \mathbf{v}_i, & \text{if } c_{\text{ave}} - \pi < c_i \leq c_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ (2\pi - \|\mathbf{v}_i\|) \frac{-\mathbf{v}_i}{\|\mathbf{v}_i\|}, & \text{if } c_i > c_{\text{ave}} + \pi \\ (2\pi - \|\mathbf{v}_i\|) \frac{-\mathbf{v}_i}{\|\mathbf{v}_i\|}, & \text{if } c_i \leq c_{\text{ave}} - \pi \end{cases}, \quad i \in [1, n]$$

29: **end for**

30: The weighted IQR Algorithm 3 is applied to the first component $v_i^1, i \in [1, n]$ of the rotation vectors to eliminate outliers, resulting in the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_1 .

31: The weighted IQR Algorithm 3 is applied to the second component $v_i^2, i \in [1, n]$ of the rotation vectors to eliminate outliers, resulting in the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_2 .

32: The weighted IQR Algorithm 3 is applied to the third component $v_i^3, i \in [1, n]$ of the rotation vectors to eliminate outliers, resulting in the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_3 .

33: The union of the index sets is computed as $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{3\text{D},\text{rot}} = \mathcal{S}_1 \cup \mathcal{S}_2 \cup \mathcal{S}_3$.

34: Return the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{3D,rot}}$.

B. Algorithm B

Algorithm 8. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Rotation Matrices in 2D Space (with Additional Criteria)

Input: A set of rotation matrices $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, a corresponding set of weights $\{w_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, and an angular threshold θ_{thres}

Output: The outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{2D,rot,precise}}$

- 1: Compute $\theta_i = \arcsin\left(\left(\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i\right)_{1,2}\right)$, where $\theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi]$.
- 2: **if** $-\pi/3 \leq \theta_i \leq \pi/3, i \in [1, n]$ **then**
- 3: No action is taken.
- 4: **else**
- 5: Apply Algorithm 6 to remove outliers in the rotation matrices.
- 6: **end if**
- 7: Apply the weighted IQR Algorithm 3 to the adjusted angle set $\{\theta_i, i \in [1, n]\}$ to detect outliers, yielding the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{2D,rot,precise}}$.
- 8: Return the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{2D,rot,precise}}$.

Algorithm 9. Outlier Removal Algorithm for Rotation Matrices in 3D Space(with Additional Criteria)

Input: A set of rotation matrices $\{\mathbf{R}_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, a corresponding set of weights $\{w_{jk}^i, i \in [1, n]\}$, and a magnitude threshold ρ_{thres}

Output: The outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{3D,rot}}$

- 1: Convert each rotation matrix into a rotation vector to obtain the set $\mathcal{V}_{\text{rot}} = \{\mathbf{v}_i = \theta_i \mathbf{n}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3, i \in [1, n], \theta_i \in (-\pi, \pi]\}$.
- 2: The corresponding set of magnitudes is computed as $\rho_{\text{rot}} = \{\rho_i = \|\mathbf{v}_i\|, i \in [1, n]\}$.
- 3: **if** $\rho_i \leq \rho_{\text{thres}}, i \in [1, n]$ **then**
- 4: No action is taken.
- 5: **else**
- 6: Apply Algorithm 7 to remove outliers in the rotation matrices.
- 7: **end if**
- 8: The weighted IQR Algorithm 3 is applied to the first component $v_i^1, i \in [1, n]$ of the rotation vectors to eliminate outliers, resulting in the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_1 .
- 9: The weighted IQR Algorithm 3 is applied to the second component $v_i^2, i \in [1, n]$ of the rotation vectors to eliminate outliers, resulting in the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_2 .
- 10: The weighted IQR Algorithm 3 is applied to the third component $v_i^3, i \in [1, n]$ of the rotation vectors to eliminate outliers, resulting in the outlier index set \mathcal{S}_3 .
- 11: The union of the index sets is computed as $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{3D,rot}} = \mathcal{S}_1 \cup \mathcal{S}_2 \cup \mathcal{S}_3$.
- 12: Return the outlier index set $\mathcal{S}_{\text{outlier}}^{\text{3D,rot}}$.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zhitao Wu: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft. **Guangyu Liu:** Resources, Supervision, Writing – review and editing.

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Outlier Detection Algorithm for Pose Graphs

Figure 2: Block diagram of the algorithm

Figure 3: Measurement without utilizing central node

Figure 4: Measurement utilizing one intermediate node

Figure 5: Measurement utilizing two intermediate nodes

Figure 6: Outlier detection results (edge density = 20%)

Figure 7: Outlier detection results (edge density = 40%)

Figure 8: APE values for selected algorithms

Figure 9: RPE values for selected algorithms